

ANALYSIS OF LEXICAL UNITS (NEOLOGISMS) USED IN “ENTREPRENEURSHIP”

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Annotation. In the current developing and Progressive Era, words are also being updated in their rhythm, filling in a new line of words. In particular, our language has grown sufficiently in the amount of new words that are used economically and in business. Neologisms related to the field of entrepreneurship are said to be new words that are being used and newly introduced in this area. Also, neologisms that are used within the framework of all spheres also arise through the means of various processes. Lexical units (neologisms) that have entered the field of Entrepreneurship are summarized in the following article.

Key words: change, divide, advise, money, carbonised cargo, current price, entry visa.

Introduction. Scientific and technical neologisms are words that express their meaning to new words in the field of Science and technology. Books, encyclopedias, newspapers, magazines, and other full-text sources may help to translate these neologisms. The content and essence of the text will be of great importance so that you can find a translation of neologisms in these sources. The use of common words that represent many specific areas: in this case, the term represents one of the specific meanings of a word. For example, the word “change” is used as an adjective in the sense of “change, divide”.

He had to **change** his money.

Discussions. 1. Universal neologisms are neologisms related to a particular technical field. For example, “Account” means “Account book”, “Accountance” means “balance sheet”, and “Advice” means “advice”, in addition to meaning “notice, notice”.

2. Special neologisms representing a field: for example, the expression “bank of circulation” means “Bank of emissia”, the expression “bank of deposit” means “deposit bank”, and the expression “bank of discount” means “Bank of account”. In such cases, these neologisms are special words regarding one area, such as the banking sector. Modern technical neologisms come across words that have different meanings in several areas. For example, the expression “current density” represents “current density”, while the expression “current price” represents

various field-specific concepts such as "current estimate". Ambiguous neologisms present specific difficulties in translation. In such cases, the context takes a special place in translation, since it depends on which area of the translator the text is translating. The peculiarities of neologisms are the pursuit of one meaning, representing clarity, process or event. In scientific and technical texts, we see that the attribute of attribution is widely used in the structure of words of the economic term. The main component is usually, in the last place. The defining component is the concept being expressed by the term, representing the nature of the process. The attributivity relation is constructed as follows:

1. [Determinant component] + [Attribution] + [principal component] Examples:

Electric motor power rating

Solar cell efficiency

Thermal conductance coefficient

This structure is used to summarize and express the meaning of neologisms using the attribute property.

Through prepositional compounds:

Table 1

A claim for money
Abandonment of goods
After-payment
Balance in hand
Bank of deposit
Balance of payment

Through the combination Noun +Noun:

Table 2

Bank certificate
Bank confirmation
Calculation number
Calendar year
Credit card
Draft budget
Export duty
Entry visa

Common quality in scientific technical texts Adjective+Noun:

Table 3

Economic growth
Foreign market
False bankrupt
Financial statements
Basic price

Participle I+ Noun :

Table 4

Briefing aids
Carrying capacity
Clearing Bank
Carrying charge
Handling capacity
Lending bank

Participle II+ Noun :

Table 5

Carbonised cargo
Packed goods
Damaged cargo
Directed cargo
<u>Declared income</u> , profit
Finished goods
Retained earnings

Indeed, attention should be paid to replacing in the text the meanings of the various items that are ambiguous or scientific and technical of the words used. Taking an example of the lbs of the business sector, the term "balance" means "balance". When "Balance of payment" is translated as "payment", the combination "balance in hand" is translated as "cash". It can mean different meanings depending on the arrival of the words in the text. For example, "balance of an account" means "balance in account" and "balance in one's favor" means "balance in someone's favor".

It is possible to prevent the correct translation of words denoting such a meaning from coming in the text in terms of meaning and essence. In this way, neologisms and lexical units require more information and concepts to properly explain the context in translation. Most translations of scientific and scientific and technical texts require the use of common ready-made colloquial words. These words are established in the scientific literature, and existing dictionaries should be used in their entirety. Since the translation of scientific and scientific and technical words is a special reserve, it is necessary to strive to determine the essence of the original word and fully use the translator's dictionary. In addition to some scientifically defined words, it is also possible that words are not fully translated in translation. However, when translating the masis of the text, it is necessary to express the content of the language. One of the main tasks of translation the content of a scientific text is to fall into the identified option. This is important for the correct and acceptable translation of meanings. One of the important tasks of the translator is also to translate according to the content, pleasant, and acceptable.

Conclusion. In entrepreneurial compound terms, simple compound terms do not have a large number of terms, but rather have the inherent advantage of expressing economic concepts correctly, with accuracy. The field of entrepreneurship includes complex and specific concepts. These lexical units represent different aspects of the economy and are very important in the analysis of economic processes. Lexical units related to the field of entrepreneurship can be related to economic theories, models, statistics and methods of analysis. These lexical unitss are important for professionals in the field of Entrepreneurship, scientific researchers and individuals who are obsessed with the practical experience of Entrepreneurship. Their clarity and compactness are important for the analysis and communication of the economy.

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